

**The Formation of Ancient Greek:
A view from construction and craft terminology***

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§1 Introduction

There are good reasons to revisit the problem of non-Indo-European substratum loans in Ancient Greek. New archaeogenetic studies have provided contexts for language contact events, while the methodologies for investigating linguistic substrata have been refined in recent years. Additionally, in the context of prehistoric archaeology, new discoveries have been reshaping older narratives regarding the Indo-Europeanisation of the Aegean. This paper presents a brief overview of the current state of the problem with the initial results of a large data-driven pilot project focusing on crafting and construction vocabulary expected to have entered Greek from a recently encountered substratum language, concluding with reflections on future prospects for investigating this material.

§2 New Contexts

The question of the time when the linguistic ancestor of Ancient Greek reached the Aegean has long been a much-debated topic in the literature.¹ The *terminus ante quem* is fairly clear; the Linear B documents from the mid-to-late second millennium BCE bear evidence of Mycenaean as dialectally differentiated Greek at the end of the Aegean Bronze Age.² The *terminus post quem* is the more difficult question, but palaeogenomic studies have been able to date the arrival of individuals bearing Yamnaya steppe-derived ancestry in Northern Greece around approximately 4200 BP (Eylem Yediay et al. 2024). Bearing in mind the caveat that data and interpretations from archaeogenetics are still rapidly developing, among the early insights from this work is that the incoming Yamnaya-steppe populations strongly admixed with the Anatolian Neolithic derived ancestries already present in the Aegean (Lazaridis et al. 2022a; 2022b). This gives context for potential linguistic contacts between the populations and a possible (but by no means only) interpretation of this data could imply social

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¹ Selectively, cf. Drews (1988), Garrett (2006), Giannopoulos (2013) for older views from different disciplinary perspectives.

² On Linear B chronology cf. Driessen (2008).

integration of the incoming and local communities through intermarriage, together with other forms of cultural, religious, and economic exchange which implies bilingual contact to some extent. Additionally, one can look to the existence of the Linear B documents themselves and the adoption of pre-existing economic structures with an administrative apparatus and writing system not originally devised for Greek as indirect evidence for language contact.³

On the side of archaeology, the renewed excavations at Pylos since 2015 have provided further contexts for linguistic and cultural exchange with the discovery of the so-called “Griffin Warrior” who appeared to Davis & Stocker (2016) to be an individual ethnically “Minoan” on the basis of grave-goods but who also evidently adopted a lifestyle of a Mycenaean warrior-elite.⁴ This individual, of course, may have been an exceptional example, but he seems to fit a broader narrative that the archaeological notions of ‘Minoan’ and ‘Mycenaean’ cultures in the second millennium BCE may have been more porous than earlier assumed. Finally, Jack Davis has also recently made the case in terms of architecture and building at Pylos, that it may well be possible that Minoan artisans could have been operating on-site.⁵

This initial discussion is not intended to be exhaustive, but rather surveys some important new extra-linguistic contexts and given these new perspectives (this is by no means a new idea, cf. de Hoz 2004), I would argue that we should explicitly frame our thinking on the early evolution of Greek as a situation that involved language contact, and additionally consider the different possibilities of prehistoric language shift a factor in the evolution of Ancient Greek. Furthermore, from Mycenaean adoption of local economic and construction technologies, we may expect construction and crafting terminology as interrelated semantic fields where we may find prehistoric loanwords in Greek as the result of recent contact with non-Greek languages in the Aegean, specifically those associated with Minoan Crete.

§3 Approaching Substrata in Ancient Greek

§3.1 *Background*

³ For recent work on Aegean scripts emphasizing script continuity over script reform, see Salgarella (2020), cf. also Steele (2024: 1–29).

⁴ It has been later reported that this individual “had no detectable Eastern European hunter-gatherer ancestry (compared with the average of $4.8 \pm 1.1\%$ for the rest of the Mycenaean-era individuals sampled at the Palace[...])” and “plausibly of entirely local Aegean origin” (Lazaridis 2022b: 943), which appears to confirm the initial archaeological assessment.

⁵ Cf. Davis (2022: 72–86) for “Minoanization” and Minoan influences at Pylos.

The idea that there are clearly identifiable non-Greek elements in the Greek lexicon has had a long research history. August Pott (1840: 451) already drew attention to lexemes with the $v\theta$ -suffix as being of probable non-Greek origin, and half a century later Paul Kretschmer (1896) predicted the existence of a non-Indo-European substratum language already before Arthur Evans's excavation of Knossos. While many of Kretschmer's initial conclusions were somewhat premature as they predated the decipherment of Anatolian and many important twentieth-century advances in Indo-European comparative linguistics, Kretschmer's groundbreaking work set the stage for subsequent work on non-Greek substrata in the Greek lexicon.⁶ Since Kretschmer other pre-Hellenic substratum theories have been put forward; see Verhasselt (2009) for a literature review of twentieth and early twenty-first century work. Three main theories have emerged which need not be mutually exclusive to one other.

- (1) Pelasgian Theory, arguing for an otherwise unattested branch of Indo-European (cf. Georgiev 1941–1945, Van Windekens 1960, Heubeck 1961, Merlingen 1963–1967)
- (2) Luvic Theory, primarily advocated for by Leonard Palmer (Palmer 1958;1980:9–16) and Margalit Finkelberg (Finkelberg 1997; 2006)
- (3) Pre-Greek (*Vorgriechisch*) Theory, a non-Indo-European substratum hypothesis first outlined by F.B.J. Kuiper (cf. Kuiper 1956), and further elaborated by his students Edzard Furnée (Furnée 1972; 1979) and Robert Beekes (Beekes 2010; 2014)

Generally, I agree with Verhasselt (2011: 298) in his critical review of recent approaches to pre-Greek substrata that the approach favoured by the Kuiper, Furnée, and Beekes, following certain criteria for identifying potential substratum vocabulary that have been broadly elaborated in recent decades in Dutch and American substratological scholarship, is likely to be the most productive approach. Recently Guus Kroonen (2024b: 4) concisely summarises these criteria:⁷

1. lack of (a consensus on) an Indo-European etymology
2. a local distribution
3. appurtenance to certain semantic fields
4. non-native morphology

⁶ Kretschmer's views further evolved in light of new material, cf. Kretschmer (1940; 1943).

⁷ Beekes gives his criteria at Beekes (2010: xxiii–xlii), Beekes (2014: 13–44). Cf. Salmons (1992: 265–267), Schrijver (1997: 293–296), Aikio (2004: 7–10), *inter alia*.

5. non-native phonology/phonotactics
6. irregular sound correspondences

Applied to Greek by Kuiper, Furnée, and Beekes, these criteria have yielded a substantial quantity of etymologically anomalous material with a wide range of unusual phonological and morphological features. Beekes (2010; 2014) used this material to reconstruct a unitary phonological and morphological system to account for the entirety of the material which has met with little scholarly consensus more broadly.⁸

§3.2 *Against the Unity of Pre-Greek*

Beekes (2010: xli–xlii; 2014: 45) has asserted that the Pre-Greek substratum is a unitary language, yet most contextual and epigraphic evidence points to the potentiality and probability of several languages at different stages (recently cf. Davis 2014: 175–181, Duhoux 2020, Meester 2024). We should expect to see some kind of lexical stratification as speakers of the variety of Indo-European ancestral to Greek migrated through the northern Balkans and into Central Greece, the Peloponnese, and the Aegean islands. Most recently recognisable are loanwords from “International” Bronze Age cultural vocabulary from other known languages (e.g. Gr. χρυσός ‘gold’ ultimately from Semitic, cf. Ugaritic *ḥrṣ*, Akkadian *ḥurāṣu* ‘gold’). But immediately below this layer are expected the “Minoan” loanwords, since Indo-European speakers adapted aspects of earlier Aegean societal structures, administration, infrastructure, and religious practices.⁹ Other substrata past this point remain more speculative, although we may postulate that a language connected to the European substratum shared with Celtic (cf. Schrijver 1997, Stifter 2010, van Sluis 2024, Meester 2024), and it cannot be further ruled out that some of these languages may have been genetically related themselves.¹⁰ If progress is to be made on this material, a methodology needs to be developed to target a specific substratum layer, for which the case study below constitutes a tentative attempt.

⁸ Cf. Meißner (2013), De Decker (2015).

⁹ There also remain outstanding problems which may never be resolved including the genetic affiliation of the language underlying Minoan Linear A. Recent work suggests it is most likely a non-Indo-European language, cf. Davis (2014: 269–277), Schrijver (2018).

¹⁰ For example, Kroonen (2024c: 305–306) draws attention to the legumes ἐρέβινθος ‘chickpea’ ὄροβος ‘bitter vetch’ with and without the characteristic *vθ*-suffix often found in Aegean substratum vocabulary which cannot be easily separated from PGmc. **arvīt-* ‘pea’ and Lat. *ervum* ‘bitter vetch’ also with and without a dental suffix.

§3.3 *Problems of Ancient Greek data*

Finally, I must address some special problems of the material under investigation. The Kuiper–Furnée–Beekes approach to Pre-Greek has assembled a wide variety of material for analysis which has been an important first step, but this material is attested from documents that span from the second millennium BCE onwards into the first millennium CE and transmitted in source material of varying reliability. This can range from (a) Classical authors with well-established manuscript traditions, (b) Greek Inscriptions from the Archaic Age to the Hellenistic and Roman periods, (c) papyri far removed from the original Aegean language contact situation, and (d) grammatical and lexical treatises from late antiquity from which a *hapax legomenon*, without any other external context or textual support, is difficult to assess linguistically. Because of the size, timespan, and different contexts of the materials and their multifaceted philological problems, it is difficult to compare two or more data out of context. To address this issue, I propose introducing some philological reliability judgements on the material (§4.3 below).

§4 **Towards an Archaeolinguistic Excavation**

§4.1 *Dataset Description*

The dataset used in this study started with the collection of “Pre-Greek” vocabulary as assembled by Beekes (2014) which built upon the work of Furnée (1972). The lexemes have been classified by individual ID numbers and further organised into ‘classes’ of quasi-cognate sets consisting of lexical variant attestations. The system of semantic classification follows the scheme used in Beekes (2014) with corrections made to individual lexemes as required. I have been further annotating this material with attestation data on the basis of standard lexical works such as the Liddell-Scott-Jones Greek-English Lexicon, epigraphic data on the basis of the Packard Humanities Institute Greek Inscriptions Database (<https://epigraphy.packhum.org/>) and other epigraphic corpora, and the *Thesaurus Linguae Graecae* (<https://stephanus.tlg.uci.edu/>). At the time of writing (January 21, 2025) the database contains 2899 tokens organised across 937 classes of vocabulary exhibiting potential substratum features.¹¹

¹¹ This larger dataset is unpublished at the time of writing but can be made available upon request.

§4.2 *Delimiting the Dataset*

To attempt to delimit a subset of this dataset where recent loans are expected, in view of the recent archaeological perspectives discussed above I suggest we should expect recent loans from lexemes in the semantic domain of construction and craft terminology. Therefore, from the larger in-progress dataset I extracted a subset of the vocabulary consisting of vocabulary and potentially related material in the semantic classifications (a) *Equipment & Utensils: Domestic and Craft Tools*, (b) *Construction: Architecture and Constructional Elements*, and (c) *Construction: Infrastructure*. This resulted in a more restricted dataset of 172 lexemes divided across 58 classes of variant vocabulary (e.g. Ion. γέφυρα vs. Cret. δέπυρα) across these and other intersecting semantic fields elsewhere in the larger dataset.¹²

§4.3 *Methodology*

To address the philological reliability problem (§3.3 above) I introduced a *relative reliability score* to each lexeme in the dataset on the basis of their attestation context on a scale of 1 (least reliable) to 5 (most reliable) with the following criteria:

1. **Very Low:** Word is marginally attested, e.g. only in Hesychius or other scholastic literature; or there is suspected scribal error (e.g. itacism)
2. **Low:** Word has limited literary attestation in Roman Imperial or late antique literature
3. **Medium:** Word has limited attestation in Classical authors, and lacks epigraphic or papyrological support
4. **High:** Word is well attested in Classical authors, possibly with late epigraphic or papyrological support
5. **Very High:** Word is well attested in Classical authors and is also attested in contemporary inscriptions from the Archaic or Classical periods

I further took the lexical classes with at least one **Very High** and at least one further **Very High** or **High** rated lexeme and classified them by the types of variation (phonological, morphological)

¹² Cf. Beekes (2014: 114–117, 124–128). A .csv-file of the dataset is permanently archived in the *Knowledge Works* Open Access repository (<https://10.17613/38akm-3m222>).

exhibited. Only these are analysed, but other cases of the same types of variation are also included. To this end, the aim of this analysis is to identify such linguistic features found on the lexemes with the best philological reliability among these lexemes in these semantic categories, and this may tentatively yield insights on what linguistic features we may expect to be diagnostic in the most recent layer of Aegean substratum borrowings.

§5 Data and Results

§5.1 *Introduction*

The following is a summary of the data attested by irregular correspondences and non-inherited derivational affixes attested in two or more lexical classes of variants from the dataset-extract. Reliability judgements follow variants in square brackets. Class numbers refer to the lexical class number in the overall dataset.

§5.2 *Phonology*

§5.2.1 voicing-alternation (cf. Beekes 2014: 14)

- Class 570: ἄτρακτος ‘spindle, arrow’ [5] ~ ἄδρακτος [1]
- Class 677: κάπετος ‘ditch, trench’ [5], σκάπετος [5] ~ σκάπεδος [5]
- Class 659: κρατευταί ‘supports for spits, stones supporting a pavement’ [5] ~ κραδευταί [5]

§5.2.2 aspiration-alternation (cf. Beekes 2014: 14)

- Class 656: θριγκός ‘topmost course of stones in a wall, cornice, frieze’ [5], θριγγός [3], θριγχός [2] ~ τριγχός [1], στριγχός [1]
- Class 574: θρῖναξ ‘trident’ [5] ~ τρῖναξ [1]
- Class 664: πύργος ‘tower, wall-tower’ [5] ~ φύρκος [1], φούρκος [1]
- Class 665: σκόλοψ, -οπος ‘pointed pole, palisade’ [5] ~ σκόλοφρον [1]

- Class 667: τέραμνα ‘house, residence’ [4], τέρεμνα [3] ~ θεράπων, -οντος ‘servant’ [5], θέραπνη [5], θεράπαινα [5], etc.
- Class 672: χλῆος ‘debris, filth’ [5], χλῆδος [2] ~ κληδόν [1], κληδέα [1]

§5.2.3 voicing/aspiration-alternation (cf. Beekes 2014: 14)

- Class 649: αἴθουσα ‘portico’ [4], αἴθουσσα [1] ~ αἴδωσσα [1]
- Class 675: κορχυρέα ‘subterranean drain’ [5], γέργυρα [2], γόργυρα [2], κορκόδρυα [1]
- Class 660: λαβύρινθος ‘maze, labyrinth’ [5] ~ *da-pu₂-ri-to-jo* [5] (NB: *pu₂* = [p^hu])
- Class 582: μάχαιρα ‘butchery-knife’ [5] ~ μάγειρος ‘butcher, cook’ [5], μάγιρος [5]

Beekes (2014:14) treats all of these alternations as the same phenomenon, but I have separated them depending on the specific alternation in phonation type. From these examples there are two Very High examples for a simple voicing alternation (Class 677 (σ)κάπετος ~ σκάπεδος; Class 659 κρατευταί ~ κρατευδαί), one High and Very High example for aspiration alternation (Class 667 τέραμνα, if truly connected with θεράπων, perhaps with an original meaning ‘house-servant’), and two Very High examples of voicing and aspiration alternation (Class 582 μάχαιρα ~ μάγ(ε)ιρος; Class 660 λαβύρινθος ~ *da-pu₂-ri-to-jo* /dap^huríntho^hjo/ if the identification of the Mycenaean lexeme is correct).¹³ This may suggest that voicing and aspiration were originally non-phonemic in the original donor language. The places of articulation remain consistent even if phonation type varies.

§5.2.4 ε/ι-alternation (cf. Beekes 2014: 24)

- Class 185: ἄρπεζος* ‘hedge, bramble-fence’ [4], ἀρπέζας [1], ἄρπεζα [2] ~ ἀπρίξ [4], ἄπριγδα [3], ἄρπισαι [1]
- Class 674: γέφυρα ‘dyke, embankment’ [5], δέπ(h)υρα [5], βέφυρα [2] ~ δίφουρα [1]
- Class 652: ἐστία ‘hearth’ [5] ~ ιστίη [5], ιστία [5]
- Class 668: τίτανος ‘chalk, lime, marble scrapings’ [4] ~ τέτανος [1]
- Class 551: ψέλιον ‘bracelet, anklet’ [5], ψελιώω ‘twine, wreath’ [2], ψέλλιον ‘bracelet, ring, anklet’ [1], σπέλλιον [1] ~ ψίλιον [5], ψίλλιον [1]

¹³ Regarding this form cf. the recent discussion of Judson (2017).

Only two classes have multiple high-reliability lexemes with this alternation: Class 652 ἔστια (Att.) ~ ἰστίη (Ion.), ἰστία (Boeot., Locr.) and Class 551 ψέλιον ~ ψίλιον.

§5.2.6 *s*-mobile (cf. Beekes 2014: 14)

- Class 677: κάπετος ‘ditch, trench’ [5] ~ σκάπετος [5], σκάπεδος [5]
- Class 656: στριγγός ‘little wall’ [1] ~ θριγγός [5], θριγγός [3], θριγγός [2], τριγγός [1]
- Class 590: σχενδύλη ‘pair of tongs’ [5], σκενύλια [3] ~ κένδυλα [1]

Only one class (Class 677 (σ)κάπετος ~ σκάπεδος) shows multiple Very High reliability lexemes for *s*-mobile. This may indicate that *s*-mobile was a feature of a more-recent substratum language, but at the same time I do not see why an explanation similar to the ones we use for inherited words showing Indo-European *s*-mobile could not be possible.¹⁴ It is difficult to judge this alternation as a diagnostic feature from this single example.

§5.2.7 *ε/α*-alternation (cf. Beekes 2014: 23)

- Class 578: μέλαθρον ‘roof, beam; house’ [5] ~ κμέλεθρον [1]
- Class 667: τέραμνα ‘house, residence’ [4], θεράπων, -οντος ‘servant’, [5] θεράπνη [5], θεράπινα [5], etc. ~ τέρεμνα ‘house, residence’ [3]
- Class: 551: ψέλιον ‘armlet, anklet’ [5], ψελιώω [2], ψέλλιον [1], σπέλλιον [1] ~ ψάλιον [4] ‘part of the bridle’, ψαλίσ, -ίδος (2) [4], ψαλίσ, -ίδος (3) [3], ψαλίσ, -ίδος (1) [2], ψαλόν [1], σπαλίσ [1]

Out of this material there is only one Very High ~ High reliability alternation: Class 551 ψέλιον ‘armlet, anklet’ against ψάλιον ‘part of a bridle, a kind of curb-chain’ and ψαλίσ, -ίδος (2) ‘subterranean arched passage, canal, subterranean vault’. The semantic connection, if the words are related, would seem to be something circular or ring-shaped in a two-dimensional plane. On the basis of these data alone it seems difficult to judge the reliability of this alternation as a diagnostic feature.

§5.2.8 (irregular) labiovelar correspondences (cf. Beekes 2014: 19–20)

¹⁴ E.g. reanalysis of nominative *-s over word boundaries, cf. Mayrhofer (1986: 119–120).

- Class 589: *qa-ra-to-ro* [5] ‘oven-rake, fire-poker’(?), Σπάλαυθρα ‘Spalauthra’ (TN) [4], σπάλαυθρον ‘oven-rake’ [1], σπάλαυθρον [1], σκάλευθρον [1]
- Class 674: γέφυρα [5], δέπ(h)υρα [5], βέφυρα [2], δίφυρα [1]

On the basis of the continuity of the Aegean Linear scripts’ *q*-series syllabograms it seems reasonable to assume that some form of labialised velars existed in the language underlying Minoan Linear A, and consequently it is not completely unexpected that irregular labiovelar correspondences occur in this material:¹⁵ Class 674 δέπ(h)υρα (Cret.), βέφυρα (Boeot., Strattis *apud* Ath. 14.622a) and δίφυρα (Lacon., Hsch. δ 1994) appear to reflect expected dialectal outcomes for *g^w, but γέφυρα (Hom.) would be unexpectedly delabialised; Class 589 *σκ^wάλα(υ)θρον is more difficult to interpret, since the best attested examples Myc. *qa-ra-to-ro* and the toponym Σπάλαυθρα are themselves interpreted through glosses transmitted in lexical and grammatical literature (cf. Hsch. σ 1399, Phot. σ 435, Poll. 7.22.1; Aura Jorro 1993: 186–197). Since labiovelar correspondences are expected from Linear A these examples should be taken strongly into consideration as potential evidence for more recent borrowing from Cretan languages.¹⁶

§5.2.9 ο ~ α alternation (cf. Beekes 2014: 23)

- Class 655: θόλος ‘round building with a conical roof’ [5], θολία ‘conical hat with a wide brim’ [2] ~ σαλία [1], *θαλιοποιοί [1], perh. also θάλαμος ‘inside room at the back of a house’ [5](?)
- Class 657: κολυβός (1) ‘bridal chamber’ [1], κολυβός (2) ‘farmstead’ [1] ~ καλύβη ‘hut, cabin’ [4], καλύπτω ‘I hide’ [5], καλυφή ‘submerged land’ [4], καλυβός ‘bridal chamber’ [4]

One Very High example of ο ~ α alternation is possible: Class 655: θόλος ~ θάλαμος, but much hinges on assuming these lexemes were derived from the same lexical root in the donor language and underwent the same underlying derivational processes. Therefore, on the basis of these data alone it is difficult to judge the reliability of this alternation as a diagnostic feature.

¹⁵ On the problem and possibility of the back-projection of LB sign values on LA, cf. Steele & Meißner (2017), Steele (2024: 1–20).

¹⁶ For the question of labiovelars in non-Greek loans see already Kuiper (1968), Beekes (1995).

§5.3 *Morphology*

§5.3.1 Introduction

Morphology is more difficult to consider since in the absence of knowing the original morphological analysis in the donor language these analyses are somewhat arbitrary; even the best-known Pre-Greek suffix *-vθ-* does not exhibit any obvious derivational semantics (cf. Chantraine 1933: 368–371). In spite of these problems, I note the following potential morphological features following the classification of Beekes (2014: 29–42).

§5.3.2 suffix *-av-* (cf. Beekes 2014: 31)

- Class 185: ἀρπάναι ‘cattle folds, enclosures for livestock’ [1]
- Class 651: βαλανεῖον ‘warm bath, bathing-room’ [5]
- Class 668: τίτανος ‘chalk, plaster, lime, marble scrapings’ [4], τέτανος [1]

§5.3.3 suffix *-v-* (cf. Beekes 2014: 37)

- Class 667: θεράπνη ‘handmaid’ (1) [5], θεράπνη ‘dwelling, habitation’ (2) [3],
- Class 588: σκέπαρνος ‘axe for working wood’ [4]
- Class 593: φάτνη ‘manger’ [5], πάθνη [2]

§5.3.4 suffix *-αρ-* (cf. Beekes 2014: 32)

- Class 661: μέγαρον ‘hall’ [5], Μέγαρα ‘Megara’ (TN) [5]
- Class 588: σκέπαρνος ‘axe for working wood’ [4]

§5.3.5 suffix *-ελλα* (cf. Beekes 2014: 33)

- Class 572: δίκηλλα ‘trident’ [5]
- Class 580: μάκελλα ‘mattock’ [4]

§5.3.6 suffix -οπ- (cf. Beekes 2014: 38)

- Class 576: κάρδοπος ‘kneading-trough, mortar’ [5], κάρδοπη ‘mortar’ (fem.) [4]
- Class 665: σκόλωψ, -οπος ‘pointed pole, palisade’ [5]

There are only a few of examples in this set: ‘kneading-trough; mortar’, ‘mortar’, ‘pointed pole’, and labiovelar suffixes are well known elsewhere from anomalous vocabulary in Greek (e.g. *a-to-ro-qo* /antʰrɔ:kʷos/ with Att.-Ion. ἄνθρωπος, cf. Kuiper 1956; 1968). It may be helpful as a diagnostic, but only if no Indo-European inherited etymology is possible.

§5.3.7 suffix -(ι)νθ- (cf. Beekes 2014: 37)

- Class 660: λαβύρινθος ‘maze, labyrinth’ [5], *da-pu₂-ri-to-jo* ‘daphurinth’(?) [5]
- Class 663: πλίνθος [5]

The appearance of the νθ-suffix is not unexpected since it has been long recognised as a feature of substratum vocabulary (cf. §3.1 above). Given its attestation on Crete with Mycenaean *da-pu₂-ri-to-jo* we may consider it a diagnostic feature of more-recent substratum vocabulary.¹⁷

§6 Conclusions

Based on this survey attempting to filter potential vocabulary from a most-recent substratum language on the basis of crafting and construction terminology and the strength of their attestations, we may summarise the best attested features as the following:

- anomalous voicing and aspiration alternations (4 or 5 Very High examples)
- ε ~ ι alternation (2 Very High examples)
- labiovelars not attributable to Indo-European correspondences (2 High ~ Very High examples)
- nominal suffix -(ι)νθ- (2 Very High examples)

¹⁷ On this suffix see recently Kroonen (2024c).

On the basis of this restricted dataset I additionally highlight the following potential candidates that show two or more of these features in their variants as the most likely to have come from a recent substratum with connection to unknown Cretan languages:

- λαβύρινθος ‘labyrinth’ (voicing and aspiration alternation, nominal suffix -(ι)νθ-)
- γέφωρα ‘dyke, embankment’ (partially irregular labiovelar correspondence, ε ~ ι alternation)

This admittedly has not resulted in a large amount of material which we might attribute to a more-recent substratum language with a great deal of certainty, but the aim of this exercise was an attempt to impose some limits on the data using external factors from archaeological contexts (lexemes restricted to semantic categories where borrowing is expected) and imposing some philological reliability controls as part of an overall assessment. Nevertheless, some recurring features in this material have been identified, and for future research it would be worth attempting this approach on other subsets of the material (e.g. societal, cultural, administrative or religious terminology) and compare results to see if similar linguistic features recur across other semantic fields where more-recent substratum borrowings are expected.

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